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EVENT SERVICE QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY IN BIDA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the direct effect of event service quality on customer satisfaction in the hospitality industry in Bida, Niger State, Nigeria. The descriptive and quantitative survey research gathered data from 150 event attendees (customers) who attended events hosted in the hotels studied. A well-structured questionnaire containing 18 items, with four demographic items was used to generate data from the respondents. The model developed for the study was validated through the reliability test with the help of SPSS. The result of the inferential statistical analysis revealed that customer satisfaction in events hosted in the hotels is driven by empathy, assurance and responsiveness. Tangibility and reliability did not make significant contribution to the model. The study concluded that, it is very important for hotel owners/manager to identify, evaluate and manage service quality dimensions that are capable of enhancing event satisfaction. The implications of the study showed that any hotel operating event halls and is desirous to enhance the degree of customer satisfaction, the hotel owners/managers ought to invest in strategies that can foster brand satisfaction through the delivery of event service quality.

KEYWORDS

Events. Tangibility. Assurance. Empathy. Responsiveness. Reliability. Customer Satisfaction.

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Introduction

Service organisations including event centres are expected to deliver value to their customers and event attendees. As a service firm, they strive towards delivering a high level of service quality in order to achieve customer satisfaction with a view to enhancing customers' positive behavioural intentions towards the organisation. To achieve this feat, organisations should develop appropriate marketing strategies capable of delivering customer value and capturing value in return.

The ability of organisations to capture value in return (profit) is dependent on delivering good customer experiences through quality products and services. This explains why Rather, (2018) argued that creating excellent customer experiences in the contemporary hospitality industry remains a credible source of differentiation strategy which is needed for competitive advantage because of its ability to generate valuable customer relationships.

Narver (2000) argued that hotels can only compete favourably if they are able to satisfy guests' needs. Accordingly, hotel owners/managers in the hospitality industry need to identify particular service attributes/elements that are capable of providing their guests more experiential value (Narver, 2000). When the hotel owners/managers are able to identify these attributes that are capable of meeting guest needs and expectations there will be improved and effective delivery of hospitality quality service product. Gilani, Forozia, and Zadeh, (2013) posited that employing customer satisfaction metrics in service evaluations and crafting of marketing strategy is crucial in the success of a hospitality company.

In extant literature, there are empirical evidence studied in various contexts to prove that service quality commonly affects customer satisfaction and consumer behavioural intentions. Examples include events at Jakarta Conference Centre, Indonesia (Wahyuningtias, Zulkarnain, Nurbaeti., & Asmaniati, 2017); sport (basketball in Japan and football in the United States of America) (Yoshida & James, 2010); festival event in Salangor (Ramil Januri & Ghani, 2018); Service quality in small hotels in in Bauchi State, Nigeria, (Dimfwina, Murtala, & Ukonu, (2018); ATM service quality in Uganda, (Katono, 2011); hotel service quality (Bayad, Bayar, Baban, Shahla, Nechirwan, Pshdar, Hassan, Bawan, Sarhang, & Govand, 2021); service quality in Nigerian banking industry (Obananya, 2020). This current study attempts to fill the gap in literature by investigating the effect of event service quality on customer satisfaction in the context of events hosted and managed by hotels in Bida, Niger State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundations

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA): This study is underpinned by the theory reasoned action. The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) predicts consumers' purchase intentions of products or services. In specific terms the theory explains the relationships between beliefs, attitudes, behavioural intentions and actual behaviour (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977). The theory was propounded by Fishbein and Ajzen (1977) specifies that the two principal factors that are determinants of behavioural intentions are a personal or "attitudinal" factor and a social or "normative" factor.

The first factor is a function of the salient (behavioural) belief which the individual has about the perceived consequences of performing the behaviour as well as the individual (outcome) evaluation of those consequences. Here in lies the connection/interest of the theory with this current study. When a celebrant (consumer) know that his accepting to host an event such as a wedding reception in a hotel

environment will enhance the quality of such event and the resultant event satisfaction of attendees, then the action/intention (behaviour) of booking for an event centre in a hotel environment becomes justifiable (Ajzen, & Fishbein, 1980).

The second component of the theory bothers on subjectivenorms which describes the actor's perception of what other people (described as important specific referent individuals or groups) think he should do and the motivation to comply with the referents. In the context of hosting events an event in a hotel environment, which is more costly but luxurious in nature than hosting it in an open field in a primary or secondary school, the celebrant may choose a hotel environment which members of his social group may likely approve of. Put differently, his social group may likely approve of his action as representing their expectations and an acceptable behavioural action (Ajzen, & Fishbein, 1980).

Conceptual Review

Event Service Quality

Service quality describes how well customer expectations are matched by the delivered service level by the service provider. When the expectations equals the delivered service customer satisfaction occurs. However, in a situation where customer expectations are higher than the perceived performance, customer satisfaction is affected negatively. (Uzunboylu, 2016). SERVQUAL was developed as a measuring tool for service quality based on the comparison of two major factors: customer perceptions of perceived service and actual service expected/expected service. As a confirmed tool for measuring service quality SERVQUAL can also be used to analyze the causes of service problems in organisations.

Service quality is very important for service organisations as it enables them to improve firm performance through customer satisfaction and positive customers' behavioural intentions. Put differently, an organization that provides a phenomenal service quality, can achieve competitive advantage in the marketplace. However, despite the number of scholars who have developed one measurement tool or the other, there seems to be no general agreement on the regarding instruments, measurements and techniques needed for the measurement of service quality (Hapsari, Clemes, & Dean, 2016). Triplett (2007) suggested that service quality is regarded as an important issue in marketing and management because of its obvious relationship to costs, profitability, customer satisfaction, customer retention and positive word of mouth and it is widely considered as a driver of corporate marketing and financial performance. In this study, our focus is in event service quality and customer satisfaction.

For this current study, it is the following dimensions: tangibility, empathy, assurance, reliability and responsiveness that are used to measure service quality in the context of event that is hosted and managed by hotels.

Tangibility: Tangibility represents physical things (tangibles) that can be felt and touched in a service environment. In context of event service quality, tangible can be referred to as equipment (sound and audio), physical facilities and their appearance (ambience, lighting, air-conditioning, seating arrangement in the event hall), and the service personnel of the organization and their uniform (Blery et al., 2009). These tangibles are essential in rendering of services by any event organization. It should be emphasized that the customers who make use of such services do assess the quality and usability of these tangibles.

Reliability: Reliability describes the ability of a service provider such as a hotel hosting events to provide the services truth fully and consistently. Customers such as wedding celebrants or meeting/conference organisers want trustable services on which they can rely.

Assurance: Assurance measures service quality in terms of the level of knowledge and courtesy displayed by the service employees in rendering the services. Assurance also involves the ability of service personnel to instil trust and confidence in customers.

Empathy: Empathy measures the ability of service employees to take care of the customers by giving them individualized attention. This implies becoming hearing ears to customers' problems and effectively addressing their concerns and demands.

Responsiveness: Responsiveness reflects of the willingness of service employees to help customers and provide prompt service. In an event management context service employees are to ensure that customers' programme runs smoothly and without delays at anytime. For example, electricity supply when disrupted should be restored in such a manner that the programme will still run smoothly.

Customer Satisfaction

Tse and Wilton (1988, p. 204) defined the concept of customer satisfaction as “consumer’s response to the evaluation of the perceived discrepancy between prior expectation and the actual performance of the product as perceived after its consumption”. Atarodian (2013, p.204) described the concept of customer satisfaction as “a level of performance that meets customer expectations”. Put differently, customer satisfaction is conceived to mean a judgment which is made by consumers based on a specific service encounter or product purchase/consumption (Cronin & Taylor, 1992)

In the hospitality industry customer satisfaction is crucial to the survival of hospitality service organisations as well as being the most studied concept in the field(Golder, Mitra, & Moorman, 2012). Customer satisfaction has been found to be an antecedent to customer/guest post consumption behavioural intentions towards the brands in various market (Li, Ye, & Law, 2013;Atarodian, 2013).Extant literature is of the view that customer satisfaction measures the degree of satisfaction provided by the goods or services of an organisation as measured and demonstrated by the number of repeat customers or how service meets the customer’s expectation(Fornell, Johnson, Anderson, Cha, & Bryant, 1996; Oliver, 1994; Oliver, 1997; Stevens, Knutson, & Patton, 1995).

Empirical Review and Hypotheses Development

Wahyuningtias, at al (2017) examined the influence of event service quality, cost, and convenience driver on event satisfaction among visitors who attended event at Jakarta Convention Center. Research design adopted was a survey with questionnaire as the main instrument for data collection. The four variables that made up the independent variable were event service quality, event cost and event convenience while event venue satisfaction served as the dependent variable. The study sample were 177 customers who had visited Jakarta Convention Center, with experience of visiting various types of events. The statistical result from multiple regression analysis method with SPSS programme showed that . The result of the inferential statistic showed that the three independent variables had no significant relationship with event satisfaction.

In an ATM service context in Pakistan, Khan (2010) investigated effect of significant dimensions of ATM (automated teller machine) service quality on customer satisfaction in the banking industry. The

questionnaire was the instrument used for primary data collection from a sample of 500 customers of the foreign (multinational) and a local bank who own and operates ATM card through a convenience sampling. The statistical results obtained through Regression analysis showed that convenience, efficient operation, security and privacy, reliability and responsiveness had positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. As claimed by the authors the study made a significant contribution to the quality management literature because few empirical studies are available dealing with this aspect of the banking sector in Pakistan.

Ramil, Januri and Ghani (2018) examined the relationship between quality of event performance and attendees' satisfaction in the context of a festival in Shah Alam, Selangor. A total of 250 attendees served as a sample of this study while the convenience sampling technique was adopted. Pearson correlation was the analytical tool used to analyze the simple relationships between the dimensions of event performance (informative, design and hedonic) and satisfaction. The statistical results revealed that there is a significant relationship between event performance and attendees satisfaction. Regression analysis was used to identify the degree with which each dimension influenced the satisfaction. The findings showed that all three dimensions of event performance significantly influenced customer satisfaction. The authors believed that the findings will help event organizers in improving the quality and performance in event industry.

In Ghana, Narteh and Owusu-Frimpong (2011) investigated the relationship between ATM service quality and customer satisfaction in the banking industry. The study used a convenience and systematic sampling methods to generate primary data from 650 ATM users of 15 banks in Ghana with a self-completion questionnaire were administered to. The statistical results by exploratory factor analysis showed that reliability, ease of use, accuracy, convenience and responsiveness are all significant dimensions of ATM service quality. Further statistical analysis showed that ATM service quality is positively related to customer service satisfaction. When treated individually, the dimensions that had significant effect on customer satisfaction were: accuracy, reliability, and convenience. The study recommended that managers who are desirous in improving ATM service experience of customers in the banking industry should focus on accuracy, reliability, and convenience dimensions of the ATMs.

Within Ibadan metropolis in Nigeria Apata, Afolabi, Ajayi, Abimbola, Adebayo, and Okhiria, (2019) investigated the implication of service quality and customer loyalty in hotels. They found that service quality had significant correlation with overall loyalty, repeat patronage and price insensitivity. Service quality was also found to significantly relates with customer loyalty.

Bayad, Bayar, Baban, Shahla, Nechirwan, Pshdar, Hassan, Bawan, Sarhang, and Govand, (2021) studied the impact of hotel service quality on customer satisfaction in the hospitality sector of the economy. Their results indicated the four service quality dimensions (empathy, responsiveness, assurance and tangible) had positive relation with customer satisfaction, except reliability that had negative relationship with customer satisfaction.

In the hospitality sector in Bauchi State, Nigeria, Dimfwina, Murtala, and Ukonu, (2018) investigated the effect of quality service of small hotels on customers' satisfaction in Bauchi state, Nigeria. They inferential statistics showed that tangibility, empathy, assurance and responsiveness had positive and significant relationship with customer satisfaction while reliability and customers' satisfaction were not positively and significantly related. In Uganda, Katono (2011) found that tangibles, card issues, reliability and location are the most important service quality evaluation dimensions of ATMs from students' perspective. The study used a convenience sample.

Understanding what constitute important service quality dimensions in a service environment is very crucial because it is critical to satisfying customers and enhances the propensity for positive behavioural intentions which is needed for organisational performance. This makes it imperative for service brands to ensure that their customers are satisfied at all times through offering them quality services.

Customer satisfaction is of great interest in services marketing. Empirical evidence exist to demonstrate that customer satisfaction is an antecedent with purchase/consumption and post-purchase behaviours such as repeat purchase, attitude change, loyalty and positive word-of-mouth (Fornell, et al., 1996; Oliver, 1994; Oliver, 1997; Stevens, et al, 1995).

From the foregoing, we therefore hypothesize that;

H1: Tangibility significantly affects customer satisfaction in events management by hotels in Bida, Nigeria

H2: Empathy significantly affects customer satisfaction in events management by hotels in Bida, Nigeria

H13: Reliability significantly affects customer satisfaction in events management by hotels in Bida, Nigeria

H4: Assurance significantly affects customer satisfaction in events management by hotels in Bida, Nigeria

H5: Responsiveness significantly affects customer satisfaction in events management by hotels in Bida, Nigeria

Research Methodology

Research design: Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this empirical study because this research involves collection of data that deal with attitude, preference, behaviour and perception of customers of events hosted in hotel environment in Bida. It should also be emphasised that descriptive survey research design helps the researcher to hypothesise several variables in measurable relationships.

Sample and data collection: data were collected from a sample of current customers of six hotels in Bida during events that coincided with the period of questionnaire administration. A sample size of 150 event attendees was gotten from the unknown population using Freund and William's formula for sample size determination from unknown population. A well-structured questionnaire was used to generate data from the respondents through convenience sampling technique. Out of a total of 150 questionnaires distributed, 120 were retrieved, and all proved useful for statistical analysis.

Demographic Profile of Respondents: The profile analysis of the respondents showed that 85 respondents (71%) were male while 35 respondents (29%) were female. In terms of age brackets, 72 respondents (60%) were within 30–39 years while 48 respondents (40%) were greater than 40 years. From the age bracket data, majority of the respondents were within the ages of 30 – 39 years. Regarding the respondents' level of education, data revealed as follows; those Higher National Diploma and Bachelor degree (HND/B.SC) were 95 (34.3%), while those with a second degree (MA/MSC/MBA) were 95 (79%) Respondents with a first degree were of the majority.

Measurement Instrument and Questionnaire design

The major instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. All the measurement items were measured on a five-point Likert-type scale anchored by: Strongly Disagree [SD](1), Disagree [D](2), Agree [A](3), Agree fairly strongly(4) and Strongly Agree [SA](5) to express the degree of agreement with the items or otherwise.

All the items were adapted from extant literature. The five dimensions of event service quality (tangibility, empathy, reliability, assurance and responsiveness) were measured using items adapted from Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry (1985) The three items used for customer satisfaction were adapted from Ryu, Lee and Kim, (2012) and Lim (2010),

Research Results

Reliability Analysis

Table 1 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.874	.878	18

The reliability of the 18-item research instrument was ascertained with Cronbach Alpha. The value of the Cronbach Alpha is .874 as shown in Table 1. This value is above the threshold value of .7 as suggested by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) which confirms that the measuring instrument is internally consistent and therefore helpful and applicable in measuring opinions of customers of events hosted at hotels.

Data Analyses

To ascertain the effect of event service quality on customer satisfaction in hypothesised relationships, multiple regression analysis was conducted.

Hypothesis 1-5 Event Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Table 4-6 Multiple Regression analysis showing the effect of event service quality on customer satisfaction.

Table 2 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.924 ^a	.853	.846	.29750

a. Predictors: (Constant), Responsiveness, Tangibility, Reliability, Empathy, Assurance

Table 3 ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	49.464	5	9.893	111.778	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.496	96	.089		
	Total	57.961	101			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Responsiveness, Tangibility, Reliability, Empathy, Assurance

Table 4 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.091	.270		.336	.738
	Tangibility	-.253	.143	-.174	-1.774	.079
	Empathy	.611	.123	.572	4.946	.000
	Reliability	-.011	.122	-.008	-.091	.928
	Assurance	.480	.152	.390	3.162	.002
	Responsiveness	.186	.066	.175	2.827	.006

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Table 2 shows that R is .924, and represents the simple correlation between event service quality and customer satisfaction which is very high. R² value (“R” Square) is .853 and adjusted R square is .846. This implies that 85.3% of the variance in customer satisfaction can be explained by the changes in independent variables of event service quality. As a general rule, this model is considered as a ‘good fit’ as this linear regression model is able to explain more than 60% (threshold) of variance in the dependent variable: customer satisfaction (Moosa& Hassan, 2015).

The *p* value .000 is <0.05 in Table 3 is an indication that the regression model statistically significantly predicts customer satisfaction which is the outcome variable. This implies that the hypothesis is supported.

Table 4 provides the multiple regression analysis for the contribution of the five dimensions of events service quality used in the study and hypothesised as H1, H2, H3, H4 and H5 respectively. The table shows that un-standardized beta (β) of tangibility, empathy, reliability, assurance and responsiveness are: ($\beta = -0.253$), ($\beta = 0.611$), ($\beta = -0.011$), ($\beta = 0.480$), and ($\beta = 0.186$) respectively. This specifies that empathy made the greatest contribution to the model.

The result of the regression analysis shows that only empathy, assurance and responsiveness ($\beta = 0.611$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$) ($\beta = 0.480$, $p=0.002 < 0.05$) ($\beta = 0.186$, $p=0.006 < 0.05$) provided by the hotels in the context of event service quality in influencing their customer satisfaction made significant contribution to explaining the dependent variable, while tangibility ($\beta = -0.253$, $p=0.079 > 0.05$) and reliability ($\beta = -0.011$, $p=0.928 > 0.05$) did not.

Therefore the model can be written as:

$$\text{Customers Satisfaction} = 0.0611(\text{EMT}) + 0.480(\text{ASS}) + 0.186(\text{REP}) + 0.091$$

The model suggest that by associating any of the three dimensions of event service quality of a hotel brand, the empirical model can increase the level of customers' satisfaction which guarantees patronage when other things remain constant. Accordingly therefore, changes in empathy of each hotel brand can have the biggest influence on level of customers satisfaction to revisit the hotel for patronage as its beta co-efficient ($\beta = 0.611$, $p=0.000 < 0.05$) is the highest and significant.

Testing of hypotheses 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5

Decision Rule

If	$PV < 0.05$	=	Hypothesis is supported
	$PV > 0.05$	=	Hypothesis is not supported

H1: The outcome of analysis show that tangibility had significant effect on customer satisfaction to the hotels in Bida ($\beta = -0.253$, $p=0.079 > 0.05$). Hypothesis H1 is therefore not supported.

H2: The outcome of analysis show that empathy had significant effect on customer satisfaction to the hotels in Bida ($\beta = 0.611$, $p=0.000 > 0.05$). Hypothesis H2 is therefore supported.

H3: The outcome of analysis show that reliability had no significant effect on customer satisfaction to the hotels in Bida ($\beta = -0.011$, $p=0.928 > 0.05$). Hypothesis H3 is therefore not supported.

H4: The outcome of analysis show that assurance had significant effect on customer satisfaction to the hotels in Bida ($\beta = 0.480$, $p=0.002 > 0.05$). Hypothesis H4 is therefore supported.

H5: The outcome of analysis show that responsiveness had significant effect on customer satisfaction to the hotels in Bida ($\beta = 0.186$, $p=0.006 > 0.05$). Hypothesis H5 is therefore supported.

Discussion of Results

Hypothesis 1 showed a non significant effect of tangibility on customer satisfaction towards hotels in Bida ($\beta = -0.253$, $p=0.079 > 0.05$). Therefore, H1 is not supported. This finding is inconsistent with the findings of Bayad, et al (2020) and Dimfwina, et al (2018).

Hypothesis 2 posited a significant effect of empathy on customer satisfaction at the hotels in Bida. With $\beta = 0.611$, $p=0.000 > 0.05$ the effect is significant. This result is consistent with the prediction of H2 and is therefore supported. Thus, a higher level of empathy on the part of service employees will

enhance event satisfaction in a hotel environment. This finding is consistent with the finding of Bayad, et al (2020) and Dimfwina, et al (2018).

Hypothesis 3 posited a significant effect of reliability on customer satisfaction at the hotels in Bida. With $\beta = -0.011$, $p=0.928>0.05$ the effect is not significant. This result is not consistent with the prediction of H3 and is therefore not supported. This finding is consistent with the finding of Bayad, et al (2020) and Dimfwina, et al (2018).

Hypothesis 4: posited a significant effect of assurance on customer satisfaction at the hotels in Bida. With $\beta = 0.480$, $p=0.002>0.05$ the effect is significant. This result is consistent with the prediction of H4 and is therefore supported. This finding is consistent with the finding of Bayad, et al (2020) and Dimfwina, et al (2018).

Hypothesis 5: posited a significant effect of responsiveness on customer satisfaction at the hotels in Bida. With $\beta = 0.186$, $p=0.006>0.05$ the effect is significant. This result is consistent with the prediction of H5 and is therefore supported. Thus, a higher level of responsiveness on the part of service employees during events will enhance customer satisfaction. This finding is consistent with the finding of Bayad, et al (2020) and Dimfwina, et al (2018).

Conclusion

The empirical study investigated the effect of event service quality on customer satisfaction in the context of events hosted in the hotel environment in Bida, Niger State. Data collected from current customers of six hotels in Bida where different kinds of events were held was used to test five hypotheses developed for the study. The empirical results supported all the research hypotheses in the context of empathy, assurance and responsiveness, while tangibility and reliability were not supported.

A very important finding of the study is the fact that among the three event service quality dimensions, empathy ($\beta = 0.611$, $p=0.000>0.05$) had the highest significant effect on customer satisfaction, followed by assurance ($\beta = 0.480$, $p=0.002>0.05$) and responsiveness ($\beta = 0.186$, $p=0.006>0.05$).

It is therefore safe to conclude by stating that the outcome of the research indicates that empathy is an important determinant of customer satisfaction followed by assurance. It is very important for hotel owners/manager to identify, evaluate and manage service quality dimensions that are capable of enhancing event satisfaction.

Implications of the Study

When customers or consumers are satisfied with service by virtue of the experiential value they receive, they are likely to become loyal to such a service brand, and as such contribute to a firm's profitability. The implication is that any hotel operating event halls and is desirous to enhance the degree of customer satisfaction, the hotel owners ought to invest in strategies that can foster brand satisfaction through the delivery of event service quality.

The current study is an attempt to examine the influence of event service quality on customer satisfaction in the hotel context. To a large extent, the findings of the study provides fruitful implications to both practitioners and academicians.

On the academic side, this current study makes a significant contribution to the service quality management literature by systematically exploring the impact of event service quality in the context of events hosted in hotels. Overall, the current study findings therefore provide tentative support to the proposition that event service quality should be recognized as significant antecedents for gaining and sustaining customer satisfaction in event marketing and management in Nigerian hotels.

On the practitioners' side, the important influence of event service quality on customer satisfaction in Nigeria is highlighted. This study therefore argue that hotel owners/managers can benefit from the implications of these findings. For instance, given the robust relationship between empathy and customer satisfaction (0.611), assurance and customer satisfaction (0.480) and also between responsiveness and customer satisfaction (0.186), marketers ought to pay attention to both employee service training and development with a view to enhancing the quality of service deliverable to the satisfaction of event attendees. Also, the non-significant relationship between tangibility and customer satisfaction ($\beta = -0.253$, $p=0.079>0.05$) and between reliability and customer satisfaction ($\beta = -0.011$, $p=0.928>0.05$) ought to be of serious concern to hotel owners/managers especially for those hotels studied. This implies that they need to identify the equipment and other physical facilities needed to satisfy event customers. They also need to promise only those services they are capable of delivering to avoid customer dissatisfaction. Eventually, the event customers will become satisfied with resultant positive word-of-mouth communication and repurchase intentions which all contribute to organisational performance.

Limitations and Future Research

Despite how useful this current study is, the research has its limitations. First and most significantly, the study can be improved upon by increasing the sample size and including participants in other geographical areas like North West, North East, South East, South West geo-political zones of Nigeria. Second, the current study was limited to only Nigerian who attended events hosted in hotels. For results comparison, subsequent researches should involve foreigners who attend events hosted in Nigerian hotels such as seminars and conferences. In the long run, however, these suggested future areas of study could elicit new knowledge to the existing body of event service quality literature in Africa.

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